

dish was infested with 3 neonate larvae and incubated at 26 °C, at 12 h light/12 h darkness photoperiod. Each treatment was replicated five times.

In all cases, larvae developed normally on susceptible Rexoro. After 20 d of infestation, neonate *S. incertulas* larvae developed to 5th instar on Rexoro callus and to 3d on Chianan 2, but failed to survive on *O. ridleyi*. At 15 d after infestation, *C. suppressalis* neonate developed to 5th instar on Rexoro, to 4th on Yabami Montakhab 47, and to 2d on *O. ridleyi*. At 17 d after infestation, *C. medinalis* neonate larvae developed to 5th instar on Rexoro and Ptb 10 calli, to 4th on IR5865-26-1, and to 2d on *O. ridleyi* callus.

Results verify the use of tissue culture to investigate rice resistance to insect pests. Further work could provide plant breeders with sensitive screening tools to develop rice germplasm with better sustainable levels of insect resistance. □

Improved sources of plant resistance to yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* Walker in rice

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Dependable sources of resistance to YSB have not been available. For example, Ratna and Sashyashree, said to have moderate field resistance to YSB, have not been resistant to heavy infestation. Since 1980, we have worked to identify better donors of resistance.

In kharif 1980 and 1986, YSB broke out at heading stage in 121 late (140 d and above) cultures and varieties in 5 experiments and seed multiplication plots, resulting in whiteheads (up to 45.7%). In kharif 1982, 1983, 1985, and 1986 and rabi 1983 and 1987, 6 planned experiments involving 352 entries (including national and international YSB screening sets, named varieties of IRRI, and repeats from earlier years) were field tested. Test plants (minimum of 4 and maximum of 16 per entry) were implanted with 24 healthy, laboratory-laid 4-d-old egg masses of YSB per hill

YSB infestation in selected test entries in different screening trials under outbreak conditions or egg mass implantation in growing plants in the field. Cuttack, India, 1980-87.

Trial	Season and year	Details of entries	Entry	Infestation (%)	
				Infestation (%)	Whiteheads
1	Kharif 1980	30 late varieties ^a	Mahsuri	5.2	
			CR1010	45.7	
2	Kharif 1980	51 late cultures ^a (replicated)	CR301-3066	nil	
			Mahsuri	2.2	
			CR259-398-326-155	2.5	
3	Kharif 1980	10 late cultures ^a (replicated)	Jagannath	42.3	
			CR260-30	nil	
4	Kharif 1980	10 late cultures ^a (replicated)	CR1016	27.4	
			CR260-30	0.3	
5	Kharif 1982	25 entries of IRTP YSB screening set + 11 others (replicated) ^b	CR1018	21.6	
			IR9828-23-1	5.5	
6	Rabi 1983	20 entries ^b	Ratna	22.8	
			W1263	9.2	
			CO 18	7.9	
			W1253	4.1	
			IR15723-45-3-2-2-2	4.8	
			CR317-166	8.0	
			IR29	19.2	
7	Kharif 1983	80 breeding lines ^b + 25 others	W1263	11.7	19.1
			IR15723-45-3-2-2-2	16.1	11.6
			IR9828-23-1	13.7	8.1
			W1253	16.6	NF
			GEB24	52.6	NF
			IR29	35.9	32.4
8	Kharif 1985	60 entries of stem borer set (DRR) + 20 others ^b			
			CR260-151-81-2-710	9.7	
			CR260-167-247-179	10.0	
			CR260-30	17.4	
			IR9828-23-1	25.0	
			IR15723-45-3-2-2-2	28.0	
			W1253	7.6	
9	Rabi 1986	30 released IR varieties + 20 other entries ^b	Sashyashree	77.3	
			RP2199-7-10-8-3	5.9	
			W1253	6.0	
			IR9828-23-1	4.3	
10	Kharif 1986	20 varieties on farm ^a	W1263	10.2	
			RP2069-39-3-1-4	39.5	
			IR20	19.2	
11	Rabi 1987	36 entries of stem borer screening, kharif 1986 (DRR) + 30 IR varieties + 15 others ^b	IR58	18.9	
			IR24	47.5	
11	Rabi 1987	36 entries of stem borer screening, kharif 1986 (DRR) + 30 IR varieties + 15 others ^b	CR1018	28.6	
			CR260-100-11	2.3	
			CR260-30	3.2	
			IR5	50.0	
			RP2199-3-3-1-6	8.8	
			IET9405 (OR437)	4.9	
			IR15723-45-3-2-2-2	4.0	
W1253	9.3				
11	Rabi 1987	36 entries of stem borer screening, kharif 1986 (DRR) + 30 IR varieties + 15 others ^b	IR9828-23-1	10.5	
			W1263	3.3	

^aYSB outbreak in field at heading. ^bYSB egg mass implantation in growing plants in field.

between 35 and 70 d after planting, and borer infestation was evaluated at 20-25 d after implantation.

Borer incidence in all 11 trials showed adequate YSB pressure on the 473 entries (see table).

CR260-30 (trial 4), W1253 (5), W1263 (5), IR9828-23-1 (5), IR15723-45-3-2-2-2 (5), and Mahsuri (2) proved consistently resistant to YSB. They are the most promising donors for use in YSB resistance breeding programs. □